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The Etiology of chronic renal failure in a sample of Iraqi patients: Lower incidence of diabetes and hypertension related renal failure.

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Abstract

Background: Chronic renal failure (CRF) is a pathophysiologic process with multiple etiologies, resulting in the inexorable attrition of nephron number and function, and frequently leading to end-stage renal disease (ESRD).The etiology of renal failure may vary according to the country of origin and little is known about the etiology of chronic renal failure (CRF) in Iraq because of the lack of central reporting agency. The aim of this study is to determine the etiology of CRF in a sample of Iraqi patients.

Patient and Methods: From 2001 to October 2005 50 patients, 33 males (66%) and 17 females (34%), with chronic renal failure were referred to a single consultant (of pediatrics and nephrology). Their ages ranged from 6 months to 81 years (Mean: 28.5).

Results: The 3 most common causes are different with chronic GN accounts for 28%, hereditary nephropathies and genetic syndromes (20%), and congenital abnormalities (16%).

Conclusion: The causes of CRF in Iraqi patients differ markedly from the causes in the western societies with markedly

lower incidence of diabetes and hypertension related renal failure.

Keywords: Chronic renal failure-Iraqi-Patients.

Introduction

Chronic renal failure (CRF) is a pathophysiologic process with multiple etiologies, resulting in the inexorable attrition of nephron number and function, and frequently leading to end-stage renal disease (ESRD).the incidence and prevalence of ESRD has increased during the last decade in many areas of the world Whereas glomerulonephritis was the leading cause of CRF in the past, diabetic and hypertensive nephropathy are now much more frequent underlying etiologies in adult patients in Western societies[1,2,3,4].The etiology of renal failure may vary according to the country of origin and little is known about the etiology of chronic renal failure (CRF) in Iraq because of the lack of central reporting agency[5]. The aim of this study is to determine the etiology of CRF in a sample of Iraqi patients.

Patient and Methods

From 2001 to October 2005 50 patients, 33 males(66%) and 17 females(34%) , with chronic renal failure were referred to a single consultant (of pediatrics and nephrology).

The patients were observed at the University hospital in Al Kadhymiyia an Al Mosawi private clinic at Al Kadhymiyia. The male to female ratio was 1.94. Patients came mainly from 5 provinces of Iraq including Baghdad,Al Anbar,kirkuk,AlBasraha,andAlNasiriyya. Their ages ranged from 6 months to 81 years (Mean 28.5). Six (12%) patients were under the age of 5 years, 13 patients(26%) their age ranged from 5 to 15 years, 11 patients(22%) their age ranged from 16 to 30 years, 9 patients(18%) their age ranged from 31 to 50 years,11 patients(22%) were above 50 years. Figure (1) shows age distribution of patients with CRF.

Figure (1): Age distribution of patients with CRF

Results

There were 14 patients with chronic glomerulonephritis (GN).A presumptive

diagnosis of GN was made by the presence of albuminuria/or hematuria

(+granular casts).Three of them each has biopsy proven focal segmental glomerulosclerosis(FSGS),Membranoproliferative GN(MPGN),and rapidly progressive GN(RPGN) respectively. Two of them have SLE and GN, and they didn't underwent renal biopsy. Ten patients have CRF caused by hereditary nephropathies and genetic syndromes including 3 patients with nephronophthisis,3 patients with nephropathic cystinosis,2 patients with adult polycystic kidney disease, and 3 patients each with polycystic disease of kidneys and liver, primary oxalosis,and oculo-cerebro-renal syndrome. Four patients have CRF caused by renal stone disease. Eight patients have CRF caused by congenital abnormalities including single kidney and unilateral hypoplasia, ectopic hypoplastic kidney with infection or obstruction, and neurogenic bladder. Two patients have reflux nephropathy. One patient has diabetic nephropathy and one patient has bladder cancer. The cause of CRF was undetermined in 10 patients. Table (1) summarizes the etiology of CRF in this sample of Iraqi patients.

21 patients didn't underwent dialysis before referral,26 patients were treated with IPD, and 4 patients were on regular or intermittent HD including one patient initially treated by IPD.One patient was observed after failure his transplanted kidney ,in whom transplantation was proceeded by IPD.One patient was transplanted few weeks after referral ,but died about one month after transplantation. The patients were followed for variable periods, and it was not possible to follow many patients for a long time. During this period of

observation 11 patients died from uremia. mainly because of a lack of proper facilities of renal replacement therapies.

Table (1):The etiology of CRF in a sample of Iraqi patients.

Chronic GN	14(28%)
Non specific	10
SLE	2
FSGS	1
MPGN	1
RPGN	1
Hereditary Nephropathies & Genetic syndromes	10(20%)
Nephronophthisis	3
Nephropathic cystinosis	3
adult polycystic kidney disease	2
Polycystic disease of kidneys and liver	1
Primary oxalosis	1
oculo-cerebro-renal syndrome	1
Congenital abnormalities: single kidney and unilateral hypoplasia, ectopic hypoplastic kidney with infection or obstruction, and neurogenic bladder.	8(16%)
Undetermined	10(20%)
Renal stone disease	4 (8%)
Reflux nephropathy.	2 (4%)
Diabetic Nephropathy	1 (2%)
Bladder cancer	1(2%)

Discussion

CRF is a major health issue in various parts of the world. There has been a dramatic increase in the incidence of ESRD as well as a shift in the relative incidence of etiologies of CRD during the past two decades in many areas of

the world. Whereas glomerulonephritis was the leading cause of CRF in the past, diabetic and hypertensive nephropathy are now much more frequent underlying etiologies. This may be a consequence of more effective prevention and treatment of glomerulonephritis or of diminished mortality from other causes among individuals with diabetes and hypertension.[1,2,3,4].

The 3 most common causes of ESRF are diabetes related ESRF (42.3%),hypertension (25.8%),and GN (10.8%).In this sample of Iraqi patients, the 3 most common causes are different with chronic GN accounts for 28%, hereditary nephropathies and genetic syndromes (20%),and congenital abnormalities (16%).

CRF was commoner in females in this sample. However this observation was similar to the observation in other countries[1,2].

Conclusion: The causes of CRF in Iraqi patients differ markedly from the causes in the western societies with markedly lower incidence of diabetes and hypertension related renal failure.

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